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Elastomer-granular fluid composites for variable compliance in robotic applications

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#ICCM22

Stiff verses soft in robotics

Rigid robotics

- Can do work on large loads.
- Possess limited degrees of freedom.
- Unable to conform to irregular shaped surfaces in their environment.

Soft robotics

- Deform under moderate forces.
- Display increased flexibility.
- Adapt and conform to their environment.

[1.]

Variable stiffness via the jamming transition

- A characteristic property of granular materials is that they undergo a jamming phase transition where they switch from flowing like a liquid to being locked into a rigid solid.
- Jamming occurs when geometric constraints among neighboring particles prevent mobility and the applied shear stress is too small to cause yielding.

[2.]

Pressure induced stiffness tuning in robotics

Universal robotic gripper

[3.]

Articulated cable-driver actuator

[4.]

Aims

Within the field of robotics, there is a growing interest in actuators with variable stiffness that may combine the best aspects of both soft and ridged robotics within a single system. Variable stiffness has been successfully demonstrated in elastomer – granular fluid composites. In this research we want to investigate the fluidic nature of these granular materials and consider them as a new medium for transferring force in pneumatic actuators.

The specific aims of this research are to:

1. To identify a granular fluid with high flowability suitable for pumping.
2. Design a fluidic system for transporting granular fluid and selectively jamming it.
3. Use granular fluid for shape change in an elastomeric actuator and the jamming transition for variable stiffness.

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